

SUBSTITUTED BUTYRO LACTONES. PART IV. SYNTHESIS OF
 γ -(2-ALKOXY-5-CHLOROPHENYL)-BUTYRO LACTONES

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Ethyl β -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionates have been reduced by aluminium isopropoxide to γ -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.

In continuation of the work described in Part III of the series (this *issue*, p. 742) γ -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones have been prepared and described in this communication. Attempt was made to succinoylate 4-chlorophenyl alkyl ethers to obtain the required β -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids. Succinoylation of 4-chloroanisole afforded β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid in 90% yield. Constitution of this acid rests on the fact that on oxidation it gives rise to a product identical (m.p. and mixed m.p. 81-82°) with methyl ether of 5-chlorosalicylic acid (Peratoner and Condorelli, *Gazzetta*, 1898, 28, 211).

In the case of higher 4-chlorophenyl alkyl ethers, the keto-acids were partially dealkylated. Therefore β -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids were prepared by alkylating ethyl β -(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionate (Trivedi and Nargund, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1942, 2, Part III, 127).

β -(2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid was prepared by the following two methods: (a) β -(2-Methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid was demethylated by hydrobromic acid in acetic acid solution and (b) 4-chlorophenol was succinoylated in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in tetrachloroethane.

Ethyl β -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionates were reduced by aluminium isopropoxide, as described by Genge and Trivedi (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 801) to obtain γ -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chlorophenyl alkyl ethers were prepared from 4-chlorophenol and alkyl bromide in presence of sodium ethoxide. 4-Chlorophenyl-*n*-propyl and -*n*-butyl ethers do not seem to have been described previously.

* In part

TABLE I

β-(2-Alkoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids and derivatives.

S. No.	Compounds.	Cryst. shape.	M.P. or B.P.	Formula.	% Chlorine.*	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>β</i> -(2-Methoxy)-P†	Needles from hot water	120°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ Cl	14.20 (244.2)	14.64 (242.5)
2.	Oxime of (1)	Plates from dil. alcohol	168°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ NCI	13.67	13.76
3.	Semicarbazone of (1)	Needles from dil. alcohol	180°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	11.57	11.85
4.	Ethyl ester of (1)		192-95°/6mm	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₄ Cl	13.31	13.12
5.	<i>β</i> -(2-Ethoxy)-P	Needles from hot water	157°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl	14.05 (257.9)	13.84 (256.5)
6.	Oxime of (5)	Plates from benzene	100°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄ NCI	13.18	13.07
7.	Ethyl ester of (5)		180-85°/3mm	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	12.70	12.48
8.	<i>β</i> -(2- <i>n</i> -Propoxy)-P	Needles from dil. alcohol	150°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₄ Cl	12.98 (268.1)	13.12 (270.6)
9.	Ethyl ester of (8)		55° 200-205°/10min	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	11.85	11.90
10.	<i>β</i> -(2- <i>n</i> -Butoxy)-P	Needles from dil. alcohol or hot water	110°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	12.70 (282.4)	12.48 (284.5)
11.	Oxime of (10)	Plates from benzene	145°	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ NCI	11.64	11.85
12.	Ethyl ester of (10)		235-40°/9mm	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ Cl	11.58	11.36
13.	<i>β</i> -(2- <i>n</i> -Amyloxy)-P	Needles from alcohol or hot water	101-102°	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	12.02 (259.9)	11.90 (298.5)
14.	Oxime of (13)	Plates from dil. alcohol or benzene	112°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ NCI	11.47	11.32
15.	Ethyl ester of (13)		235-40°/4mm	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₄ Cl	10.68	10.87
16.	<i>β</i> -(2- <i>n</i> -Hexyloxy)-P	Needles from dil. alcohol or hot water	106°	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ Cl	11.23 (310.2)	11.36 (312.5)
17.	Ethyl ester of (16)		200-205°/6mm	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₄ Cl	10.29	10.42
18.	<i>β</i> -(2-Hydroxy)-P	Do	178°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₄ Cl	15.90	15.53
19.	Semicarbazone of (18)	Needles from dil. alcohol	248°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	12.32 (286.3)	12.44 (285.5)
20.	Ethyl ester of (18)	Do	80°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl	13.62	13.84
21.	Methyl ester of (18)	Do	50°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ Cl	14.59	14.64

†P stands for -5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid.

*Figures within parantheses represent equiv. wt's.

4-Chlorophenyl-*n*-propyl ether is a colorless liquid, b.p. 224-25°/760 mm, d_4^{40} 1.092, n_D^{40} 1.570. (Found : Cl, 20.70. C₉H₁₁OCl requires Cl, 20.80%).

4-Chlorophenyl-*n*-butyl ether is a colorless liquid, b.p. 240°/760 mm, d_4^{40} 1.098; n_D^{40} 1.508. (Found : Cl, 19.13. C₁₀H₁₃OCl requires Cl, 19.24%).

β -(2-Methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid was prepared in 90% yield by succinoylating 4-chlorophenyl methyl ether as described in Part III (*loc. cit.*).

β -(2-Hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic Acid.—(a). A mixture of β -(2-methoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid (50 g.), acetic acid (100 c.c.) and hydrobromic acid (250 c.c., 48%) was refluxed for 2 hours on a sand-bath. The (2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acid, separating on cooling, was filtered and washed with water (yield 70%). It crystallised in needles from hot water, m.p. 178°.

(b). To a cooled mixture of 4-chlorophenol (25.6 g., 0.2 M), succinic anhydride (20 g., 0.2 M) and tetrachloroethane (200 c.c.) was added powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (54 g., 0.4 M) in three lots, with stirring. It was then heated on an oil-bath at 120° for 2 hours. It was decomposed with ice and HCl and the keto-acid was recovered as usual after removing tetrachloroethane by steam distillation; yield 40%. Acid obtained by method (b) is identical (mixed m.p.) with that obtained by method (a).

Ethyl β -(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionate was obtained from this acid by the usual procedure.

TABLE II

 γ -(2-Alkoxy-5-chlorophenyl)-butyro lactones and derivatives.

S. No.	Compounds.	Cryst. shape.	M.P. or B.P.	Formula.	% Chlorine.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	γ -(2-Methoxy)-L		185-90°/3mm	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	15.35 (222.3)	15.67 (226.5)
2.	S-salt of γ -(2-methoxy)-HB	Plates from hot water	102°	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	8.80	8.67
3.	γ -(2-Methoxy)-HB	Plates from benzene	100°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl	14.80 (245.9)	14.52 (244.5)
4.	γ -(2-Ethoxy)-L		240-45°/3 mm	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl	14.95 (242.0)	14.76 (240.5)
5.	γ -(2-Ethoxy)-HB	Plates from benzene	103°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl	11.07 (259.8)	10.91 (258.8)
6.	γ -(2-n-Propoxy)-L		215-20°/7 mm	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl	13.82 (251.6)	13.95 (254.5)
7.	γ -(2-n-Propoxy)-HB	Plates from benzene	105°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	13.18	13.02
8.	γ -(2-n-Butoxy)-L		220-25°/4 mm	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	12.98 (265.3)	13.22 (268.5)
9.	S-salt of γ -(2-n-butoxy)-HB	Plates from hot water	85°	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	7.92	7.86
10.	γ -(2-n-Amyloxy)-L		215-16°/4 mm	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ Cl	12.80 (284.1)	12.57 (282.5)
11.	S-salt of γ -(2-n-amyloxy)-HB	Do	85°	C ₂₇ H ₃₁ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	7.54	7.62
12.	γ -(2-n-Hexyloxy)-L		224-30°/3 mm	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ Cl	11.70 (293.9)	11.98 (296.5)
13.	S salt of γ -(2-n-hexyloxy)-HB	Do	80°	C ₃₄ H ₃₉ O ₄ N ₂ ClS	7.33	7.40

HB stands for 5-chlorophenyl- γ -hydroxy butyric acid.

L " " " " butyro lactone.

S " " S-benzyl isothiuronium.

β -(2-Alkoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionic acids were prepared by alkylation of ethyl β -(2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-propionate and subsequent hydrolysis (Trivedi and Nargund, *loc. cit.*).

Ethyl β -(2-alkoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl) propionates were reduced by aluminium isopropoxide, and the lactones were isolated as described by Genge and Trivedi (*loc. cit.*), yield 40-50%.

The compounds prepared are shown in Tables I and II.

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